

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035819

GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER

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ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

WP No	Del. Rel. No	Del No	Title	Lead beneficiary
4	D4.2	D22	Networking Event for Early Career Researchers #2	CU

Nature	Dissemination Level	Related to Del. No (if applicable)
Other	Public	D4.2

Description (short)
<p>The ENLIGHT “Research and Innovation agenda with and for Society” (RISE) project aims at establishing foundations and initiating implementation of a joint research and innovation (R&I) agenda within the ENLIGHT European University Alliance.</p> <p>Work package 4 has two specific projects. 4.1 To plan a series of events to support networking/leadership skills for early career researchers (ECRs), and 4.2 is the Researcher Assessment working group. On Wednesday, June 14th, 2023, the second event pertaining to the 4.1 work package took place from 1400-1530 CET. Titled "Academic Careers - The Fun and the Obligations," the event was conducted online. Professor Ingrid Molema, University of Groningen, was the guest presenter.</p>

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1. Project background

As outlined in the project description ENLIGHT RISE aims to *'enable a world-class joint R&I agenda within ENLIGHT RISE we will need to ATTRACT AND RETAIN THE BEST RESEARCHERS in Europe and beyond, while promoting an inclusive leadership culture in keeping with the broader mission of ENLIGHT'*.

Work package 4 is led by Comenius University Bratislava (CU) with co-leads Ghent University and the University of Galway.

To develop attractive career frameworks for researchers, we launched complementary solid actions to support early career development within the alliance through **networking**, **mentoring**, and **leadership training**. One of the critical engagements of ENLIGHT is to create a balanced network across different social, economic, and geographic areas in Europe, with careful attention to the way expertise and opportunities are shared across the network, and to develop a supportive structure for talent development, career guidance, and business ideas.

ENLIGHT RISE nurtures its human capital, an essential foundation for a competitive joint R&I agenda. Building on the **ENLIGHT doctoral network's skills** workshops (part of the ENLIGHT Erasmus+ project), we expanded to create a **network of early career researchers** (post-docs, early-career faculty, <10 yrs. from PhD.) to foster fruitful research collaborations on the ENLIGHT flagship challenges and stimulate research mobility. It is envisaged that the researcher's digital matching tool (WP1) will facilitate the matching of researchers from different universities and at different stages of their careers.

The first event was planned to take place in M12, August 2022. Still, it was felt that the timing was not attractive, so a two-month extension was applied to plan/host the event by the end of October 2022 when the envisioned target group would not be on holiday or during the mayhem of university re-openings in September/early October.

2. Event Planning

The insights gained from the initial event led to the scheduling a second event in June 2023. This timeframe was chosen to ensure maximum appeal and avoid potential conflicts with the target audience's vacation plans.

As is customary for event planning, the team leader and co-leaders of the work group discussed various topics and options for the upcoming event. After consulting with members from the other six universities, decisions were made regarding:

- Hold the event online;
- Date of event: 14 June 2023
- Topic – 'Academic Careers – the fun and the obligations'
- Duration of event – 1,5 hours

- Communications strategy
- Presenters – agreed that team leads would source the speaker
- Registration/event management/feedback etc. – was agreed to be managed by Comenius University Bratislava

Professor Ingrid Molema, University of Groningen, was identified by the leads as the most suitable guest speaker. A registration portal was created, and the event was held using MS Teams.

An event flyer was designed using the ENLIGHT template to promote the upcoming event. A meeting was held on May 15th by WP 4.1 partners to discuss and come to an agreement regarding communication methods. Everyone present had the chance to ask any questions they had. It was decided that PhD. researchers could attend WP 4.1 events (since R1 was the most significant group represented during our first networking event), while WP 4.2 events were reserved for post-PhD researchers, adhering to project guidelines. Additionally, a question was added for attendees to help determine future event topics in support of ENLIGHT. We also took into consideration topics from past feedback forms.

3. Communications/Promotion

Firstly, the event flyer was emailed to all nine universities within the alliance for their internal distribution. Universities were responsible for their internal promotion of the event. The ENLIGHT communications team promoted the event via the ENLIGHT website, calendar, newsletter, and social media channels.

<https://enlight-eu.org/university-about-us/news-events/759-workshop-for-phd-students-academic-careers-the-fun-and-the-obligations>

Reminders were sent to the partner universities to further disseminate the event in the week preceding the event.

An event reminder was sent to all those registered the day before the event.

4. Speaker

Team leads from Comenius, Galway, and Ghent identified the guest speaker.

Professor dr. G. (Ingrid) Molema has a very diverse academic career and is passionate about the talent development of early career researchers. In collaboration with the dean of the University of Groningen Graduate Schools, she was responsible for the design and development of the new 'Career Perspectives Series' for PhD students. Professor Molema is an active member as an advisor/trainer of the University of Groningen Talent Development team and Groningen Graduate Schools. Additionally, she is involved in other endeavours:

- Chair of the ZONMW COVID-19 grants committee;
- Member of the University of Groningen Committee Scientific Integrity;
- Member of the North American Vascular Biology Organization (NAVBO) diversity, equity, and inclusion committee;
- Chairperson of the ZONMW PTO (Translational Research Program) evaluation committee;

- Co-founder of Vivomicx;
- Founder of ThnkSmRt bv;
- Teacher in high school (science) programs;
- Member of the recommending committee of the 'Stichting Nardus';
- Expertise in Targeted Drug Delivery; Microvascular Endothelial Pharmacology; Endothelial Biomedicine; Angiogenesis; Inflammatory diseases, sepsis, cancer; In vitro-in vivo translation; Drug Development.

Professor Molema offered valuable advice on how to invest time and energy to shape and cultivate a successful academic career. Her tips included strategies for building a research portfolio, achieving teaching excellence, gaining mobility experience, and forming positive networks.

5. Event Data

Registrations by 13th June 2023 — **287**

UPV/EHS	UBx	CU	NUI GALWAY	UGent	UGOE	RUG	UT	UU	Other*
45	24	26	28	39	24	7	56	24	14

* Other: People who registered using personal email accounts and didn't specify university choice.

Attendees on 14th June 2023.

As per the initial MS Teams report, **147** was the maximum number of attendees who attended the online event (as per unique IDs). There were some last-minute cancellation notices and requests for the recording post-event.

The event was attended by almost 150 participants, including PhD. researchers, postdoctoral researchers, research fellows, professional support staff, and other academic positions. They engaged in discussions about academic career paths, their motivations and ambitions, and the expectations of external parties that are important in their field. Professor Molema mentioned what academic employers and panel members who judge grant proposals look for and how early career researchers can make the best of their itinerary.

Event schedule:

- 1400 – 1405** **Opening introductions/allowing time for people to join/request to record the event**
- 1405 – 1410** **Brief introduction of ENLIGHT and Professor Molema by organizer**
- 1410 – 1500** **Professor Molema, 'Academic Careers – the fun and the obligations**

1500 – 1525 Discussion and Q&A

1525 – 1530 Closing comments and distribution of feedback questionnaire

6. Feedback post-event

At the end of the session, all attendees were given a feedback form /QR code. Participants were also sent the feedback form/link after the event. Forty responses were received, which accounted for over 27% of attendees. The attendees were asked the following questions:

To which job area/title do you most closely align?

PhD Researcher	Postdoctoral Researcher	Research Fellow	Professional support staff	Academic staff	Other
65%	20%	2,5%	7,5%	2,5%	2,5%

Gender

Female	Male	Non-binary	Blank
67,5%	25%	5%	2,5%

On a scale of 1 to 5 (5 being the highest) how would you rate this workshop?

5	4	3	2	1
52,5%	30%	15%	0%	2,5%

List 1-3 things you found most useful about this event?

The team received 27 replies of feedback regarding the question of what you “found most useful about this event”. Informativeness was the most popular aspect, followed by clarity and practicality. This indicates that early career researchers are on the lookout on information regarding job opportunities and career planning. The team will take this into account when deciding when planning (topics of) future events.

What do you think could have made this event better?

There were 21 replies to this question, with most respondents indicating that everything was satisfactory. However, a few individuals requested additional specific examples.

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What other events would you like to recommend as part of this Leadership Skills programme?

According to the survey, 57.5% of the participants expressed their desire to continue with career planning topics, while managing research teams was the least preferred topic, with only 27.5% of the votes. Although respondents were given the option to suggest their own topics under the 'other' category, none of them made any recommendations. The results indicate a balanced outcome.

7. Recommendations and lessons learned.

The event's goal was to bring together diverse viewpoints and exchange experiences on how to support early career researchers so they will enjoy their future endeavours in academia.

The awareness-raising campaigns, stakeholder communication, and personal online meetings were successful in generating the expected feedback. The most significant outcome of the campaign was the invitation of Professor dr. G. (Ingrid) Molema from the University of Groningen, who shared her experience of her academic career journey with early career researchers including PhD. students, post-docs, and early-career (faculty) researchers as a guest speaker.

Individual outreach (through personal contacts or personal recommendations) followed by personal (online) meetings proved to be the most effective. The main goal was to identify relevant stakeholders and discuss potential collaboration on projects in the attractive career frameworks for researchers vertical.

The feedback document furthermore proved that early career researchers are very much on the lookout for more general information on these topics.